

LECTURERS' PERCEPTIONS ON INCLUSION OF STUDENTS WITH DISABILITIES IN NIGERIAN COLLEGES OF EDUCATION: THE CASE OF FCT COLLEGE OF EDUCATION ZUBA, NIGERIA

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Abstract

This study examined lecturers' perceptions of the inclusion of students with disabilities into colleges of education in Nigeria with FCT College of Education Zuba as a reference point. Two research questions and one hypothesis were derived for the study. The 200 lecturers at FCT College of Education Abuja formed the population of the study. The sample comprised 90 lecturers, who were drawn using a stratified random sampling procedure. A 20-item questionnaire was developed by the researchers titled Lecturers' Perception on Including Students with Disabilities into Nigerian Colleges of Education Questionnaire (LPISDNCOEQ). It was organised on a four-point likert scale. The validation of the instrument was carried out by one expert in special education and one in measurement and evaluation. The research questions were answered by utilizing mean and standard deviation, while t-test was used to test the hypothesis at a 0.05 level of significance. The findings, as revealed in the study, showed that lecturers had negative perceptions regarding the inclusion of students with disabilities in Nigerian colleges of education. It was also found that there was no significant difference in the lecturers' perceptions based on gender. Based on the results of the study, a conclusion was drawn and recommendations were made, some of which include: that higher education institutions should provide workshops to expose lecturers to the fundamentals of disabilities and inclusive education; and that there is a need to provide lecturers with information regarding disability-related laws and regulations in the country.

Keywords: Lecturers' perceptions; Colleges of education; Students with disabilities; Inclusion

Introduction

The Universal Declaration of Human Rights of 1948 stated that every person has a right to education. According to UNESCO (2008), Articles 28 and 29 of the Convention of the Rights of the Child of 1989 stipulate that the education of the child shall be directed to the development of the child's personality, talents, mental and physical abilities to his or her fullest potential. Article 2 of the same convention warns against discrimination of a child of any kind based on race, colour, religion, disability, or any other status. The World Declaration of Education For All (EFA) conference held in Jomtien Thailand in 1990 as stated by Okoroikpa and Oluka (2017) put it that every

child, youth and adult shall be able to benefit from educational opportunities designed to meet their basic learning needs.

The above and other declarations on education notwithstanding, the majority of persons with special needs continued to experience different forms of barriers to achieving their educational aspirations. Such barriers cannot be surmounted by continuing with separate arrangements and schools for individuals having one kind of special educational needs or the other. Thus, as an alternative, a very different approach to education was needed which could respond effectively to the diversity of learners' needs. This gave rise to another world conference for deliberations.

In June 1994, a world conference on special needs education: Access and quality was held in Salamanca, Spain. The communiqué adopted at the end of the conference is popularly called the Salamanca statement and framework for action. It was adopted by 92 governments including 24 African governments in which Nigeria is one and 25 international organisations. The major issue of the statement is inclusive education. According to the Salamanca Statement of Action, the fundamental principle of inclusion is that all children should learn wherever possible regardless of any differences they may have. This statement symbolizes the universal approach to the Education for All (EFA) by the United Nations.

Despite the worldwide pursuit of inclusion, a universally accepted definition of it is elusive thus far due to conceptual difficulties in defining it, including what counts as evidence of its model practice (Berry, 2010; Flecha & Soler, 2013; Florian & Black-Hawkins, 2011). As currently implemented in the industrialized world, inclusion or inclusive education can be interpreted as the philosophy and practice for educating students with disabilities in general education settings (Bryant, Smith, & Bryant, 2008). The practice anchors the notion that every student should be an equally valued member of the school culture. In other words, students with disabilities benefit from learning in a regular classroom, while their peers without disabilities gain from being exposed to students with diverse characteristics, talents and temperaments.

Adediran (2008) citing Centre for Studies in Inclusive Education (CSIE), maintained that it is a practice of bringing children and young people with and without disabilities to learn simultaneously in regular preschools, primary schools, colleges and universities with appropriate arrangements for support. Ugwu's (2015) definition of inclusion explains that it means having every student/pupil educated in the same school setting with the slightest form of restriction where there is no marginalization, separation or bias. Inclusion in the education system is about seeking the ways general school structures (physical, human and material), curriculum contents and classroom lessons are planned and implemented so that all children with or without disabilities can take part and learn in the absence of discrimination or marginalisation. It is all all-encompassing in moulding the personality attributes of individuals with special needs learning alongside others without special needs in the same school environment. It also connotes discovering approaches to build up familiarity, companionship, and acquaintances reciprocated among all students as well as rapport in the midst of students, teachers and other staff in the school. Thus, this educational system which is all-inclusive promotes the training of skills, academics and character along the line that determines the development of individual, society and nation.

Nigeria in recent times, has instituted some policies in the education sector such as the National Policy on Education (2014), the National Policy on Special Needs Education in Nigeria (2015), the National Policy on Inclusive Education in Nigeria (2017), and the Discrimination against Persons with Disabilities (Prohibition) Act (2018). All this calls attention to the implementation of inclusive education in addition to other schemes. However, the population of students with disabilities in the country's colleges of education is few compared to those of them that enroll and graduate from primary and secondary schools. It was observed by Papadakaki, Maraki, Bitsakos &

Chliaoutakis (2022) that not many students with disabilities have the possibility of gaining admission into higher education; many of those admitted suffer some academic setbacks and some have the tendency to drop out of institutions more than their counterparts without disabilities. Because of their disabilities, these individuals are also prone to experiencing numerous difficulties such as marginalisation from mates, not having sympathetic consideration by the school authorities and some restrictions in accommodation (Thompson-Ebanks, 2014).

In view of the fact that the country's colleges of education exist as educational institutions where knowledge should be passed on to the students without discrimination, some students have one disability or the other whose needs ought to be attended to. Furthermore, the mere fact that an individual has a disability congenital or acquired the disability after birth should not impede the pursuit of higher education especially when he is qualified for such institutions. For instance, many students with disabilities may just complete their primary school education; some could complete secondary school education while only a few were able to make it to college. Many students with disabilities who gain admission into colleges of education drop out as a result of the non-provision of facilities that they need to ease their learning and also the emotional and psychological treatment they receive from lecturers and significant others. In a similar situation, Papadakaki et al (2022) stated that the standards of inclusive education notwithstanding, it will be challenging to attain the goals due to the fact that institutions of higher learning prove to be passive concerning the adjustments needed to contain students with disabilities. In their mind, disability issues are predicaments affecting some or very few people and therefore should be treated by specialized arrangements not knowing that modifying the educational environment is all that is needed in order to include students with disabilities. As indicated by Riswari et al (2022), they erroneously believe that disability is the inability in everything including attending lectures which can obstruct them in the process. It therefore, behooves the lecturers, and administrative officers in the colleges to make room for the inclusion of students with disabilities in their respective departments or courses of study. Students with disabilities, like others, should be at liberty to take their desired courses within their abilities.

Statement of Problem

In the present day, the impression that disability is inability to perform is still prevalent in some African countries of which Nigeria is one, despite the efforts and drive that have been garnered across the globe from the UNESCO 1994 declaration. Some lecturers still find it difficult to include students with disabilities in their classrooms due to a lack of awareness and training in the field of disabilities. This has led to a gap in the admission of students with disabilities into colleges of education in the country and it requires a critical study that needs to be genuinely considered. Although, in recent times, there has been awareness regarding inclusive education and the barriers for students with disabilities in attaining their education, research investigating the link between lecturers' perception is scarce to the knowledge of the writers. Studies on teacher's experiences with students with disabilities carried out in Nigeria have mostly focused on primary and secondary school-aged students. Equally, research that centre on how lecturers' view inclusion is scarce. This study therefore bridges the gap to investigate how lecturers in colleges of education perceive students with disabilities being enrolled into the colleges.

Purpose of study

The general purpose of this study is to explore the perceptions of lecturers on the inclusion of students with disabilities in the classroom in colleges of education.

Specifically, the study aims to:

1. examine lecturers' perceptions on the inclusion of students with disabilities in the classroom.

2. find out if there are differences in the lecturers' perceptions based on gender

Research questions

The following research questions will guide the study:

1. What are lecturers perceptions on the inclusion of students with disabilities in the classroom
2. What are the perceptions of lecturers on the inclusion of students with disabilities in the classroom based on gender

Hypothesis

1. There is no significant difference in the lecturers' perceptions of including students with disabilities in college education classrooms based on gender.

Methods

This research utilised a descriptive survey method. The study made use of a population which comprised all the 200 lecturers in FCT College of Education Zuba Abuja. The sample comprised 15 lecturers from each of the 6 schools in the college namely: Arts and Social Science, ECCE and PED, Education, Languages, Sciences and Vocational and Technical Education. This sample was selected by the use of stratified random sampling method. This was achieved by dividing the research subjects into sections from each school. The same was done within the schools based on departments. Then in the last part, the subjects were randomly selected from each of the sections which resulted in having 90 lecturers as the sample of the study.

The researchers developed a questionnaire titled Lecturers' Perception on Including Students with Disabilities into Colleges of Education Questionnaire (LPISDCOEQ) which was the instrument used for the study. It consisted of 20 items and the responses were rated on a 4-point Likert scale of Strongly Agree (SA) 4 points, Agree (A) 3 points, Disagree (D) 2 points and Strongly Disagree (SD) 1 point adapted from Oweikpodor, & Onafowope, (2022). The validation of the instrument was carried out by one specialist in special needs education and one in measurement and evaluation and both of them from the school of education, FCT College of Education Zuba. It was accepted as valid after their screening. In order to find the reliability of the instrument, the researchers used the test-retest method to check consistency within a period of 4 weeks using 30 respondents from the same FCT College of Education Zuba who were not among the selected sample used in the study. Pearson Product Moment correlation was used to link the two sets of scores to determine the reliability of the instrument. 0.78 reliability coefficient was obtained which indicated acceptability that the instrument was reliable. The researchers personally shared copies of the questionnaires with the sampled lecturers in their different schools in the college and collected them and filled them on the spot. Hence, the complete number of copies of the questionnaire retrieved was 90.

Mean ratings and standard deviation were utilised in analysing the research questions. A mean score of 2.50 was resolved as the rule to be the cut-off point for agreeing to an item. In testing the hypotheses, the t-test was used at a 0.05 level of significance.

Findings

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation analysis of lecturers’ perception on inclusion of students with disabilities in Nigerian colleges of education.

S/N	ITEM STATEMENTS		SD	DEC.
1	Special education lecturers teaching students with disabilities are preferable to general lecturers teaching them.	3.36	0.99	A
2	My relationship as a lecturer with students with disabilities will not be good enough.	2.94	0,89	A
3	Inclusive education will have negative effects on the social development of the other students	3.01	0.89	A
4	General lecturers lack the necessary skills to support students with disabilities.	3.78	0.74	A
5	Concentrating on students with disabilities is not workable as it is with other students in the classroom.	2.99	0.75	A
6	Students with disabilities are likely to display problematic behaviours in a classroom that is inclusive	2.80	0.70	A
7	If learners with disabilities are included in my classroom, it would make my lectures difficult.	2.21	1.05	D
8	Students without disabilities may mimic the behaviour of students with disabilities, which could be detrimental.	3.12	0.78	A
9	Inclusive lecture halls are likely to experience confusion due to students with disabilities.	2.89	0.72	A
10	Students without disabilities can benefit from having students with disabilities present in the same classroom.	2.18	0.55	D
11	Inclusion positively impacts the social and emotional growth of students with disabilities.	2.82	0.83	A
12	The inclusion of students with disabilities will demand thorough training for regular lecturers.	3.59	0.86	A
13	Certain lecturers are incapable of adjusting the curriculum to help students with disabilities in regular lecture halls.	2.52	1.01	A

14	Relationships between students with disabilities and their classmates are not cordial	3.15	0.96	A
15	Keeping control in a lecture hall where students who have disabilities can be quite demanding.	2.94	0.74	A
16	Learners with disabilities should receive special help outside the regular lecture hall.	1.91	1.36	D
17	Including students with disabilities into the general classroom might impact their emotional growth negatively.	3.48	0.87	A
18	Inclusive education will limit level of academic performance of the students with disabilities	3.01	0.75	A
19	Auxiliary support staff is needed for students with disabilities in a general lecture hall	3.75	0.69	A
20	In general, lecturers' communication with students with disabilities is not smooth	2.10	0.84	D

The data on Table 1 indicates that sixteen (16) out of the twenty (20) items (1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 8, 9, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 17, 18 and 19) had means greater than the decision mean of 2.50. By implication this shows that the respondents are in agreement with the researchers' statement on the negative perceptions of lecturers on including learners with disabilities in Nigerian colleges of education. However, four (4) items (7, 10, 16 and 20) had means less than the decision mean of 2.50. The responses showed that the lecturers generally have the perception that does not favour including learners with disabilities in Nigerian colleges of education.

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation analysis of lecturers' perception on inclusion of students with disabilities in Nigerian colleges of education based on gender.

S/N	ITEM STATEMENTS	MALES			FEMALES		
		\bar{X}	SD	DEC.	\bar{X}	SD	DEC.
1	Special education lecturers teaching students with disabilities is preferable to general lecturers teaching them.	3.27	1.08	A	3.44	0.90	A
2	My relationship as a lecturer with students with disabilities will not be good enough.	3.53	0.82	A	2,34	0.96	D

3	Inclusive education will have negative effects on the social development of the other students	2.85	0.71	A	3.16	0.79	A
4	General lecturers lack necessary skills to support to support students with disabilities.	3.61	0.63	A	3.95	0.85	A
5	Concentrating on students with disabilities is not workable as it is with other students in the classroom.	3.12	0.78	A	2.86	0.72	A
6	Students with disabilities are likely to display problematic behaviours in a classroom that is inclusive	2.99	0.75	A	2.61	0.65	A
7	If learners with disabilities are included in my classroom, it would make my lectures difficult.	2.15	0.91	D	2.27	1.19	D
8	Students without disabilities may mimic the behaviour of students with disabilities, which could be detrimental.	3.45	0.86	A	2.79	0.70	A
9	Inclusive lecture halls are likely to experience confusion due to students with disabilities.	2.60	0.65	A	3.18	0.80	A
10	Students without disabilities can benefit from having students with disabilities present in the same classroom.	2,14	0.54	D	2.22	0.56	D
11	Inclusion positively impacts the social and emotional growth of students with disabilities.	2.05	0,81	D	3.59	0.85	A
12	The inclusion of students with disabilities will demand thorough training for regular lecturers.	3.51	0.91	A	3.66	0.81	A
13	Certain lecturers are incapable of adjusting the curriculum to help students with disabilities in regular lecture halls.	3.38	0.96	A	1.67	1.05	D
14	Relationships between students with disabilities and their classmates are not cordial	3.12	0.78	A	3.17	1.14	A
15	Keeping control in a lecture hall where students who have disabilities can be quite demanding.	2.59	0.65	A	3.29	0.82	A
16	Learners with disabilities should receive special help outside the regular lecture hall	1.75	1.16	D	2.07	1.15	D
17	Including students with disabilities into the general classroom might impact their emotional growth negatively.	3.65	0.71	A	3.31	1.03	A
18	Inclusive education will limit level of academic performance of the students with disabilities	3.13	0.78	A	2.89	0.72	A

19	Auxiliary support staff is needed for students with disabilities in a general lecture hall	2.80	0.70	A	2.69	0.67	A
20	In general, lecturers' communication with students with disabilities is not smooth	1.54	1.04	D	2.56	0.64	A
Grand mean (\bar{X})		2.86			2.89		

Table 2 displays the analysis of lecturers' perceptions using means and standard deviation on including students with disabilities into colleges of education in Nigeria based on gender. The aggregate mean score of the males was 2.86 while that of the females was 2.89. Despite the fact that the male lecturers as well as their female counterparts had mean scores that were higher than 2.50 which was the decision mean, there was a slim disparity between them in favour of the female lecturers.

Table 3: The t-Test analysis showing how significant different the perceptions of the lecturers are on including students with disabilities in Nigerian colleges of education on the basis of gender. (*****)

Gender	N	Mean	SD	df	t-cal	Critical t	Remarks
Male	45	2.86	0.81				
				88	0.15	1.65	Not Significant
Female	45	2.89	0.79				

Data on table 3 above indicated a t-calculated of 0.15 that is less than the t-critical which is 1.65 and df of 88 at 0.05 level of significance. Thus, by this analysis, no significant difference is found between male and female lecturers' perception on including students with disabilities into the regular lecture halls. Hence, the null hypothesis is sustained.

Discussion

Going by the results of this study, the analysis of data on table 1 indicates that the responses of the lecturers are not supportive of including students with disabilities in colleges of education. In affirmation to this, Papadakaki et al (2022) stated that the standards of inclusive education notwithstanding, it will be challenging to attain its goals because institutions of higher learning prove to be passive concerning the adjustments needed to contain students with disabilities. It was also asserted by Riswari et al (2022), that such institutions erroneously believe that disability is inability in everything including attending lectures which can obstruct them in the process. The grounds for the unsupportive lecturers' point of view could be as a result of being deficient in the awareness and lacking groundwork training in the special needs education area.

Furthermore, the result as presented in table 2 and 3 showed that the variation in the lecturers' responses on the inclusion of students with disabilities in Nigerian colleges of education was insignificant based on gender. This is in consonance with Kraska (2003) in a study to ascertain postsecondary students with disabilities and perceptions of

faculty members. Kraska observed that value for the one-way analysis of variance for gender was not significant at the .05 level. This however goes contrary to the study by Llorent et al. (2020) who discovered significant gender differences in favour of female lecturers who were more eager and passionate in practicing programmes of inclusion than their male counterparts. From this, it can be inferred that the probability of differences in perceptions between males and females could occur by chance.

Conclusion

This study sought to find out how lecturers perceive the inclusion of students with disabilities in Nigerian colleges of education classrooms. From the analysis of data carried out, the study concluded that lecturers perceived the inclusion negatively indicating that integrating students with disabilities into the Nigerian colleges of education regular lecture classes is challenging. It is also concluded that showed that the variation in the lecturers' responses on the inclusion of students with disabilities in Nigerian colleges of education was insignificant with regards to gender.

Recommendations

Going by the results of this research work, the recommendations that follow are made:

1. Higher education institutions should provide workshops aimed at exposing lecturers to the fundamentals in disabilities and inclusive education.
2. There is the need to provide lecturers with information regarding disability related laws and regulations.
3. There should be investment in short term specialised training such as sign language and other methodologies to support lecturers in finding ways of how to implement inclusive education in colleges of education.
4. Societal attitude towards disability issues need to be changes through the media, campaigns and other advocacy programmes.
5. Social partnerships amongst different stakeholders in the colleges such as students, lecturers, administrative staff for a welcoming campus environments for students with disabilities.

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